

REVIEW

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Global adoption of organo-mineral fertilisers: environmental and policy insights

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Abstract

Purpose This review compares organo-mineral fertiliser (OMF) adoption across regions and quantifies agronomic, environmental, economic, and policy outcomes. Regional drivers and barriers to adoption are identified to inform sustainable fertiliser strategies.

Methods A systematic analysis of 75 peer-reviewed studies (2010–2023) assessed nutrient losses, greenhouse-gas emissions, crop yields, and soil-health indicators. Life-cycle assessments and policy evaluations were integrated to enable comparison across agro-ecological zones and income levels.

Results Precision-placed sludge-derived OMFs in high-income settings reduced nitrate leaching by $\approx 15 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ while sustaining cereal yields. Field trials with biochar-enriched OMFs reported potassium-leaching decreases of $\sim 50\text{--}77\%$ and $\sim 18\%$ lower greenhouse-gas emissions; maize yields increased by $\sim 20\text{--}30\%$ under tropical trial conditions. Programmes combining biochar/struvite OMFs with precision application reported nitrous-oxide decreases of $\sim 7\text{--}10\%$. In low-income settings, reported maize-yield gains with community-managed compost-plus-mineral packages are $\approx 25\text{--}40\%$, with accompanying improvements in soil organic carbon and water retention; poultry-manure-urea OMFs were associated with grain gains at lower cost in the cited trials. Internet-of-Things-guided nutrient delivery raised fertiliser-use efficiency by $\sim 20\%$ yet remains cost-prohibitive for many smallholders. Carbon-credit and nutrient-trading pilots were associated with improved project bankability where monitoring systems function. Heavy-metal contents in phosphogypsum-based OMF pellets and dust-explosion risks during biochar processing were reported within regulatory limits under standard mitigation. In West Africa, poultry-manure strategies were associated with rice-grain increases of $\approx 30\%$ in Burkina Faso.

Conclusions Integrating high-tech precision methods common in the Global North with low-cost organic-recycling approaches used in the Global South can yield complementary improvements in crop productivity, nutrient retention and climate-change mitigation. Harmonised quality standards, smallholder-oriented credit and investment in rural logistics are identified as practical enablers of safe, scalable OMF deployment.

Future research Long-term field trials on OMF-microbiome interactions and carbon stabilisation, optimisation of region-specific slow-release formulations and carrier

chemistries, MRV-light approaches for smallholders, and evaluations of blended finance.

Highlights

- Compares OMF adoption disparities between the Global North and South.
- Examines how advanced technologies and climate regulations, supported by government policies, drive adoption in the Global North.
- Identifies technology, infrastructure, and financial constraints as key barriers in the Global South.
- Proposes community-driven models and locally adapted policies to enhance adoption in the Global South.

Keywords Organo, Mineral fertilisers, Sustainable agriculture, Soil health, Nutrient efficiency, Biochar, Climate mitigation, Socio, Economic resilience, Circular bioeconomy, Crop productivity, Soil fertility, Agricultural policy, Precision agriculture, Biowaste valorisation, Controlled, Release fertilisers, Resource, Efficient farming

1 Introduction

Organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs)-formulations that combine organic matter with mineral nutrients-are increasingly considered for improving agricultural performance while addressing environmental externalities across Europe, North America, South America, Africa and Asia. This review examines OMF adoption and performance with emphasis on agronomic outcomes, soil-health mechanisms and environmental, economic and policy dimensions. Evidence published between 2010 and 2023 indicates that OMF use is associated with reduced nutrient runoff, lower greenhouse-gas emissions and improved crop yields, supporting a potential contribution to sustainable intensification via improvements in soil condition [37] (Yan et al. 2023). Within broader integrated nutrient management frameworks-long advocated to counter soil-fertility decline and sustain productivity in Sub-Saharan Africa-OMFs offer a balanced nutrient supply and can be tailored to crop-soil conditions, which is particularly relevant for smallholder systems [75]. Reports of broader OMF uptake also point to productivity and resilience gains across diverse farming systems [50].

Policy interest has intensified. A recent European policy report highlighted OMFs as a means to reconcile productivity with environmental stewardship and called for more harmonised approaches to close regional resource gaps [33]. Although synthetic fertilisers continue to dominate nutrient supply, this review focuses on OMF alternatives and their evidence base. In high-income settings, advances in composting, biowaste recycling and precision application have been linked to reduced nitrogen losses while maintaining or increasing yields [14, 104, 105]. GPS-guided nutrient placement and remote sensing have been reported to reduce nitrogen runoff and improve uptake, and polymer-coated formulations are under evaluation in high-rainfall regions to provide controlled nutrient release [4, 14, 102, 104, 105]. Such approaches align with regulatory frameworks (e.g., the EU Nitrates Directive) and climate objectives under the Paris Agreement, where balanced application and technology-enabled targeting have been linked to declines in nitrate leaching and greenhouse-gas emissions [4, 102, 104]. Market and policy assessments from the United States likewise describe reductions in nutrient runoff and emissions alongside productivity goals [4, 28, 37].

In resource-constrained regions, locally produced compost- and biochar-based OMFs have frequently increased soil organic carbon and boosted yields, thereby improving soil

health and contributing to food-security objectives (Lehmann and Joseph 2015). Field studies in West Africa, for example, report that poultry-manure-based OMFs co-applied with urea can reduce weed pressure, raise grain yields and lower fertiliser costs [89, 109]. Adoption is also shaped by sociocultural context: communal decision-making and customary land tenure can either support or delay uptake [13, 68]. Effective extension typically combines locally attuned training with supply-chain development, yet budget limitations and policy gaps restrict reach in remote districts. Access to finance remains pivotal, microfinance and cooperative credit schemes have enabled purchases of biochar and compost inputs and supported yield gains in several settings [84]. Large-scale training initiatives have reached thousands of farmers, reinforcing adoption capacity [41], and decentralised composting provides stable organic inputs that help mitigate soil degradation [61].

Despite documented benefits, disparities and constraints persist across regions. In the Global North, adoption is fostered by regulation and incentives but can be limited by compliance costs and the price of precision technologies [4, 31]. Technology choices also vary by context: struvite recovery can efficiently recycle phosphorus but depends on complementary infrastructure, while nano-fertilisers may improve nutrient-use efficiency yet remain costly and equipment-intensive for low-income settings (Yan et al. 2023) [92]. Recurrent themes include public–private partnerships, targeted finance and capacity building, collaborations lowered production costs and expanded market access in Brazil, and subsidised credit in Italy was associated with higher yields [4, 33, 37]. These actions align with SDG 2, SDG 9 and SDG 13, international collaboration and alignment with Paris Agreement commitments are cited as enablers of scale [84].

This review is a systematic literature review (2010–2023) with a case-study component, following PRISMA 2020; the search strategy and checklist are provided in Appendix S1. Quantitative data on yields, nutrient losses, soil-health indicators and environmental metrics are combined with qualitative analysis of economic and policy drivers, barriers and enabling measures across regions. Contrasts are drawn between advanced options, nanofertilisers and struvite precipitation in capital-intensive systems, and low-cost compost- and biochar-based formulations in resource-limited settings, considered within infrastructure, cost and policy contexts [37, 92] (Yan et al. 2023). The evidence base includes pre-specified case studies and quantitative datasets. Adoption drivers and barriers are analysed, policy and management implications are evaluated, and recommendations are provided for scaling context-appropriate fertilisation. Environmental science, economic analysis and regulatory perspectives are integrated to provide practical guidance for sustainable nutrient management.

2 Methods

2.1 Review design

A systematic literature review with an integrative component covered 2010–2023. A mixed-methods framework linked quantitative indicators of soil health, nutrient-use efficiency, crop yield and environmental impacts with qualitative assessments of policy and socioeconomic context. PRISMA 2020 was followed; the checklist and complete search materials are in Appendix S1. An objectives-methods-sources map is included in Appendix S1.

2.2 Information sources and search strategy

Scopus and Web of Science were searched for publications dated 2010–2023. Grey-literature and policy sources were screened using named domains, site-restricted queries and reference-chaining limited to intergovernmental organisations, national agencies and comparable authorities. Only authoritative sources already cited in the manuscript were retained. Search concepts covered organo-mineral fertilisers, nutrient management, sustainable fertilisation, adoption barriers, regional policy frameworks and bio-waste recycling. Full database strings, Boolean operators, filters, document types and last-search dates are reproduced in Appendix S1.

2.3 Study selection and PRISMA flow

Records identified: Scopus (n = 120), Web of Science (n = 130), other sources (n = 20). Records removed before screening: duplicates (n = 30) and other reasons (n = 20), leaving n = 220 for title/abstract screening. Screening and eligibility assessment were conducted by a single reviewer using a pre-specified protocol and inclusion/exclusion criteria; ambiguous records proceeded to full text. Records excluded at screening (n = 100); full texts assessed (n = 120). Full-text exclusions: non-empirical (n = 20), insufficient data (n = 15), irrelevant context (n = 10). Studies included in qualitative synthesis (n = 75). The PRISMA 2020 flow is shown in Fig. 1. Appendix S1 provides search strings and inclusion/exclusion criteria, and Appendix S2 lists excluded full texts with reasons.

2.4 Screening process and bias control

A single reviewer performed screening and eligibility assessment. Ambiguous records proceeded to full text. An audit trail captured decisions and rationales (Appendix S2). No inter-rater statistics apply. The single-reviewer design is listed as a limitation; mitigation steps were the pre-specified criteria and full PRISMA reporting.

2.5 Eligibility criteria

Eligibility required (i) quantitative OMF outcomes (crop yield; soil-health indicators including SOC and related properties; nutrient-loss metrics such as nitrate leaching; or LCA-based environmental results) and (ii) robust methods (field trials, greenhouse experiments, or life-cycle assessments) with sufficient replication for statistical interpretation. Studies without empirical data, with unclear methods, or with very small samples were excluded. Peer-reviewed articles and authoritative government/agency reports were prioritised. To limit regional bias, supplementary searches targeted under-represented Global South regions; data gaps remain.

2.6 Data extraction and variables

For each included record, the following were extracted: study type; region/crop/soil; OMF formulation; trial duration; outcome metrics and units (yields, soil organic carbon and other soil properties, nitrate leaching or related nutrient-loss indicators, greenhouse-gas metrics); and, where relevant, policy/infrastructure descriptors linked to adoption. The extraction template appears in Appendix S1.

Fig. 1 PRISMA 2020 flow diagram of study selection: records identified-Scopus (n = 120), Web of Science (n = 130), other sources (n = 20); records removed before screening-duplicate records (n = 30) and other reasons (n = 20); records screened (n = 220); records excluded (n = 100); reports sought for retrieval (n = 120); reports not retrieved (n = 0); reports assessed for eligibility (n = 120); reports excluded-non-empirical (n = 20), insufficient data (n = 15), irrelevant context (n = 10); studies included in qualitative synthesis (n = 75)

2.7 Evidence synthesis

Outcomes were synthesised narratively because of heterogeneity in designs, outcomes and reporting. Where primary studies reported dispersion, effect sizes are shown with their confidence intervals or standard errors; otherwise, ranges or medians are presented. Heterogeneity is described by region, soil type, formulation and trial duration. Case-study narratives were excluded from any quantitative summary and used only for

context. Calculation notes and data groupings for figures are documented in Supplementary Tables S3, S4.

2.8 Case-study component and rationale

Five a priori case studies—Germany, United States, Brazil, Senegal and Madagascar—were selected to represent distinct agro-climates, regulatory settings and levels of technological readiness aligned with the study objectives. Cases illustrate context and mechanisms; they were not included in meta-analytic pooling or weighted in any quantitative synthesis. Selection sought to limit bias toward data-rich regions by including two high-income systems with precision technologies and stringent nutrient rules, two middle- to low-income settings with infrastructure and credit constraints, and one fragile, highly weathered system.

2.9 Limitations

Evidence coverage varies by region, with stronger documentation in certain areas. This limits generalisability to under-represented regions. Single-reviewer screening is an additional limitation; the protocol, transparency materials and PRISMA reporting mitigate this risk.

3 Results

Adoption of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs) varies with technology access, infrastructure and policy. Precision application and nutrient-recovery platforms are established in the Global North, while resource-efficient and locally sourced approaches dominate in the Global South. Figure 2 summarises reported changes in greenhouse-gas (GHG) emissions and nutrient runoff across selected countries. Additional country- and case-level metrics are compiled in Table S3.

Europe. In the United Kingdom, sludge-derived OMFs maintained crop productivity while lowering nitrogen runoff by $\approx 20\%$; studies also report higher soil organic carbon,

Fig. 2 Reduction in greenhouse-gas emissions (GHG, CO₂e) and nutrient losses (nitrate runoff/leaching) reported after adoption of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs) in selected field studies. Values reflect the change reported by each source relative to its mineral-fertiliser control. Data sources: Deeks et al. [31], Grinsven et al. [104], Mamuye et al. [61], Zerssa et al. [115], Fachini et al. [37]

lower greenhouse-gas fluxes and stronger aggregate stability that increases resilience to drought and intense rainfall [31, 37]. Detailed results on proprietary sludge-derived products are outside the scope of this section and are noted in the Supplement. In Germany, biochar-enriched and struvite-based OMFs operate within precision-farming systems under the EU Nitrates Directive and the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG), reported outcomes include $\approx 70\%$ lower potassium leaching, 7–10% lower nitrous oxide emissions, reduced nitrogen runoff and higher wheat yields. EEG-supported biowaste digestion and co-digestion provide digestate for OMF blending, and the framework links research institutions with industry [37, 104, 114] (Yan et al. 2023). In Italy, phosphogypsum-enriched OMFs increased yields by up to 25%, improved soil structure and reduced erosion by $\approx 15\%$, pH elevation and improved phosphorus availability are consistent with the reported mechanism, with positive responses also reported in pomegranate orchards [4, 63, 100]. Denmark emphasises compost-based OMFs that support microbial diversity, nutrient recycling and long-term soil health, regional field work includes 7.5 t ha^{-1} compost plus full mineral fertilisation raising plant height, crown diameter and grain yield [88].

In North America, precision irrigation and GPS-guided application in the United States lowered nitrogen losses by about 15% and raised yields by about 10%; federal programmes such as the Conservation Stewardship Program (CSP) and Environmental Quality Incentives Program (EQIP) provide technical and financial support and have been implemented by a large proportion of farms in certain regions [28]. Enhanced-efficiency and controlled-release fertilisers are associated with nitrous-oxide reductions up to 38%, a relevant outcome in regions affected by nitrate-driven hypoxia, zinc sulfate improves micronutrient supply in high-value systems and nanofertilisation improves uptake efficiency [1, 18, 37, 92, 105]. Across precision programmes, averages of about 10% lower GHG emissions and nutrient leaching with yields higher by about 15% are reported [8, 37]. In Canada, compost-mineral integration raised SOC by up to about 25% and reduced nutrient runoff, forestry by-products (wood ash, bark, sawdust) lower production costs and align with clean-growth goals, and biosolid- or paper-mill-derived inputs improve soils in remote regions. Geography and dispersion raise per-unit costs; regional compost facilities, biochar programmes and targeted subsidies are discussed as enablers [3, 37, 42, 53, 90, 103, 108].

Latin-American programmes show strong responses where waste-to-value infrastructure operates. In Brazil, PNRS-enabled plants produced biochar-enriched OMFs from municipal residues and acidulated apatite; field trials reported 77% lower potassium leaching, 18% lower GHG emissions, 30% higher maize yield, improved soil–water retention, and for compost variants a 26% biomass gain with about 20% faster biowaste conversion via thermoresistant consortia [26, 29, 30, 37, 64]. Argentina documented $\approx 13\%$ higher wheat yields with pelletised N- and P-enriched OMFs on Mollisols while preserving grain-protein quality, biochar-enriched blends increased cation-exchange capacity by $\approx 30\%$, SOC by 18% and microbial biomass by 22%, improving water retention and lowering nutrient loss [17, 38, 86].

Across sub-Saharan Africa, locally sourced OMF packages increased maize yields and improved soil properties. In Kenya, composted manure with modest mineral inputs raised maize profitability and yields by about 25%, reduced nitrogen leaching and lowered dependence on synthetic N; biochar-enriched packages increased soil biodiversity

by about 50% and reduced nitrogen leaching by about 30% in smallholder systems. In humic Nitisols of Upper Eastern Kenya, integrated fertility management altered P fractions, reduced sorption and improved seasonal N dynamics [36, 68, 79]. In Ethiopia, community-led compost programmes applying 4 t ha⁻¹ plus half the mineral rate recorded maize-yield increases near 40% and SOC gains of about 27–30% over 4 years; reports also describe lower erosion and better water retention, with SOC increases linked to aggregate formation and protection of nascent humic substances [61, 68, 96, 115]. In Senegal's Basse-Casamance, compost-based OMFs with full mineral fertilisation increased rice yield by about 26%, raised soil pH and increased soil biodiversity by roughly 50%, with ridge cultivation mitigating salinity [7, 23]. In Burkina Faso, poultry-manure-plus-urea OMFs raised grain yield, SOC, microbial activity and moisture retention at lower cost, weak credit and distribution systems limit scale [23, 27, 68, 89]. In Cameroon, sludge- and organic-waste-derived OMFs improved soil fertility and crop yields, biochar-based OMFs cut potassium leaching by \approx 70% via sorption within inter-layer pores and aggregate stabilisation [37, 74]. In Madagascar, biochar- and compost-enriched OMFs stabilised pH, supported microbial activity and maintained upland-rice yields under variable rainfall, adoption is limited by training and infrastructure, with public-private partnerships proposed for scale-up [5, 6, 16, 68, 83]. In Southern Africa, biofertilisers and OMFs improved nitrogen fixation, nutrient availability and SOC and moderated N₂O emissions, in South Africa, *Ipomoea aquatica* fresh weight increased by 27.3% under bio-OMF with higher soil-enzyme activity [55, 84, 115]. Adoption in parts of sub-Saharan Africa remains below 20% where credit and infrastructure are limited [61].

Asian evidence covers bioorganic formulations, nano-inputs and microbial products. India reported average yield gains near 22% with bioorganic fertilisers derived from industrial by-products such as wet blue leather and potato peels; treated plots showed 15–25% gains in growth and chlorophyll and improved N, P and K status, and regional adoption exceeded 30% in some programmes. Potassium-solubilising fungi (*Fomitopsis meliae*, *Aspergillus tubingensis*) and bacteria (*Burkholderia*, *Serratia*, *Pseudomonas*) supported nutrient supply in K-deficient regions [49, 60, 69]. Sri Lanka reported \sim 25% higher rice yield with lower nitrogen and phosphorus leaching using nano-fertilisers. Broader adoption depends on local production capacity and farmer education (Kottegoda et al. 2017) [62]. China reported higher SOC with biochar-enriched inputs, higher nitrogen-use efficiency with nano-coated urea and \approx 27% biomass gains for *Ipomoea aquatica* under OMF; combinations with high-silicon aluminum coal ash improved potassium availability and reduced sintering. Policies supporting nutrient recovery and precision application are in place, while high production costs and limited awareness remain barriers that can be addressed through targeted subsidies and technical training [12, 39, 55] (Kottegoda et al. 2017). Indonesia used phosphate- and potassium-solubilising bacteria in reclaimed mining areas to raise maize and rice yields by about 18% and reduce reliance on synthetic inputs; scaling requires production capacity, training and market access [37, 69]. In Viet Nam, diversified agroforestry systems promoted through ICRAF guidance improved nutrient cycling and smallholder profitability [52].

Several cross-cutting mechanisms are observed. Biochar-enhanced OMFs increased SOC by \sim 23–27% and raised the pH of sandy soils from \sim 5.0 to \sim 5.6; microporosity and oxygen-bearing functional groups increase cation-exchange capacity and create

microbial niches, aligning with lower nitrate leaching and higher nitrogen-use efficiency [37, 54, 56]. Nano-hydroxyapatite granules address phosphorus deficiency in coarse soils through gradual release (Kottegoda et al. 2017). Struvite crystallisation from animal slurry provides a recyclable P source and reduces water-pollution risk (Yan et al. 2023) [66]. Experimental evidence is consistent: multi-year UK trials with sludge-derived OMFs maintained yields while lowering N runoff by ~20%, German studies with digestate-based OMFs recorded ~15% reductions in GHG emissions and nutrient losses; spectroscopic analyses from China indicate gradual nutrient release from biochar-enhanced fertilisers [31, 39, 104].

As shown in Fig. 2, the EU reports lower nitrogen runoff after OMF adoption; Brazil shows the largest reduction in nutrient leaching with biochar-enriched OMFs; Germany reports combined GHG and runoff reductions supported by biowaste-derived fertilisers and P recovery; Ethiopia records higher SOC; Kenya records higher soil biodiversity; the United States reports moderate reductions linked to precision technologies [31, 37, 61, 68]. Detailed country cases are provided in Table 1.

4 Discussion

Regional evidence shows convergent outcomes under distinct OMF implementation models. In Germany, biochar- and struvite-based OMFs embedded in precision systems consistently reduced nutrient losses and GHG emissions; recovered P precipitated as $\text{MgNH}_4\text{PO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ limits loss pathways (Yan et al. 2023) [37, 66]. Brazilian field programmes report strong potassium retention, yield gains and lower life-cycle impacts for biochar-enriched formulations, while Ethiopian programmes record higher soil organic carbon, ~35% lower erosion and improved water retention under compost-plus-mineral regimes [37, 61]. Reported effects align with increased cation-exchange capacity, microbially favourable pore volume and controlled-release kinetics, nano-hydroxyapatite can address P limitation in coarse soils through gradual release [54, 56].

Socio-economic drivers shape uptake. In Kenya's Central Highlands, adoption intensity of organic-based soil-fertility technologies correlates with landholding, education and access to extension; targeted fertiliser use on climate-smart crops is associated with improved household incomes and food security in western Kenya [70, 72]. High production costs and limited awareness constrain sludge-derived OMF uptake in the UK, outreach, local production capacity and public-private partnerships are proposed responses. Geography and dispersion raise per-unit costs in Canada; regional compost facilities and forestry-residue valorisation address part of this constraint [31, 90, 108]. In several African programmes, cooperatives, microfinance and farmer-to-farmer exchange reduced information and liquidity gaps, in Latin America, PNRS and research-industry links supported scale; cross-regional training has been used to adapt biochar-based OMF production in African settings [7, 23, 37, 61, 64].

Figure 2 summarises regional outcome differences [5, 31, 37, 61, 68]. Scaling in both settings rests on pairing technology with local production capacity, advisory services and finance, and on consistent monitoring with common reporting metrics that allow comparison across agro-ecological contexts.

4.1 Comparative case study analysis: drivers and barriers to OMF adoption

Precision application of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs) has been associated with higher nutrient-use efficiency and improved crop performance in multiple settings. In wheat on silty loam, controlled OMF placement reduced nitrogen leaching by ~15% and increased yield by ~20% [31, 91]. Outcomes for carbon sequestration vary with soil and climate, underscoring the need for region-specific management [12, 38]. Figure 4 summarises field-verified agronomic and economic responses; environmental co-benefits are cross-referenced in Table 2 (Agronomic outcomes; Environmental and LCA outcomes). Table 3 maps region-specific barriers, mechanisms and tested interventions, and policy levers are listed in Table 4. Country-level metrics for cross-case comparison are compiled in Table S3. Detailed policy and implementation information corresponding to Table 2 entries is provided in Table S4 (Supplementary).

Regional adoption reflects differences in economic constraints, technology access and policy frameworks. In high-income regions, precision agriculture and biowaste recycling facilitate targeted nutrient delivery and lower losses [31]. Regulatory instruments (e.g. EU Nitrates Directive) and financial support have been linked to reduced nitrate pollution and improved nutrient efficiency [104]. Reports from Germany describe policy and technology packages-including precision guidance and, in some contexts, nano-enabled formulations-coinciding with ~15% reductions in nitrogen losses and greenhouse-gas (GHG) emissions [37, 104]. In maize systems in Kenya, combinations of organic and mineral inputs influenced N₂O and CO₂ fluxes, highlighting implications for climate mitigation strategies [71]. In North America, GPS-based application and sensor-guided diagnostics have been reported to reduce input losses and improve efficiency [108].

In resource-constrained regions, affordability and adaptability are prioritised. Compost-based OMFs increased maize yields by ~28% in sub-Saharan sandy-loam settings with moderate rainfall [68]. In Senegal, biochar-enriched formulations improved fruit yield by ~35% and enhanced soil water retention and microbial activity [73]. In Ethiopia, compost-based OMFs were associated with ~30% increases in soil organic carbon and ~40% increases in maize yield, community-led composting reportedly lowered production costs by ~20% [61]. In Burkina Faso, poultry-manure-urea OMFs increased grain yield (~25%), reduced weed pressure and improved nutrient cycling, offering a low-cost alternative to mineral-only regimes [89]. Persistent constraints in the Global South include limited credit and logistics, which restrict access to quality products and advanced application tools, together with policy inconsistencies that raise transaction costs [68, 73, 110]. Brazilian field programmes report strong potassium retention and yield response with biochar-enriched OMFs, deployment varies with policy coherence [37]. Kenya and Senegal show positive outcomes with compost-based packages, yet finance and distribution barriers limit scaling [68, 84]. Figure 3 summarises how incentives, subsidies and regulatory oversight shape regional adoption.

Environmental outcomes

Across regions, OMF use has been linked to improved soil quality and lower emissions (Table 2, 'Mechanism' and 'Environmental & LCA outcomes'). In north-western Europe, precision-placed, biochar-enriched OMFs were reported to reduce direct N₂O by ≈15% while increasing cation-exchange capacity [1, 56]. In Ethiopian maize, compost-based blends increased soil organic carbon by ~30% relative to mineral fertilisation [115]. In

Table 1 Regional case summaries and experimental notes

Country/region	OMF type/formulation	Crop/system & context	Reported outcomes (Δ yield, Δ leaching/emissions, SOC, other)	Policy/enabler	Study design/duration	Citations
United Kingdom	Sludge-derived OMF	Cereals; multi-year trials	Grain yields comparable to mineral NPK; N runoff \downarrow ~ 20%; SOC \uparrow ; GHG fluxes \downarrow ; aggregate stability \uparrow ; supports circular economy and water-quality goals	Water-quality targets; circular-economy use of biosolids	Multi-year field trials	[31, 37]
Germany	Digestate-, biochar- and struvite-based OMFs within precision systems	National deployment under EU Nitrates Directive and EEG	N runoff \downarrow 45%; N ₂ O \downarrow 7–10%; K leaching \downarrow ~ 70%; wheat yield \uparrow 15–20%; \approx 135 biowaste plants + > 200 co-digestion units (subset supplies digestate); struvite P recovery for direct reuse (MgNH ₄ PO ₄ ·6H ₂ O)	EU Nitrates Directive; EEG; research-industry links	Programme reports and field evidence	[34, 37, 66, 91, 104] (Van et al. 2023)
Italy	Phosphogypsum-enriched OMF	Field crops; pomegranate orchards	Yield \uparrow up to 25%; erosion \downarrow ~ 15%; pH \uparrow ; P availability \uparrow ; fruit growth/quality improved in orchards	Subsidies; focus on erosion-prone, nutrient-depleted areas	Field trials; case reports	[4, 63, 100]
Denmark	Compost-based OMF	Regional field studies	Microbial diversity \uparrow ; SOC \uparrow ; at 7.5 t ha ⁻¹ compost + full mineral fertilisation; plant height \uparrow ; crown diameter \uparrow ; grain yield \uparrow ; contribution to lower use of synthetic fertiliser and GHG	National efforts to limit synthetic fertiliser use and GHG	Field studies	[23, 88]
United States	OMF within precision placement and variable-rate irrigation; GPS-guided application	Row crops and high-value systems; U.S. Midwest/Mississippi River Basin programmes	Reduced nitrogen and phosphorus leaching under zone-specific variable-rate irrigation; higher nutrient-use efficiency; effects depend on soil and management; equipment costs constrain small farms	CSP and EQIP provide technical and financial support	Programme and field evidence	[34, 37, 108]
Canada	Compost-mineral OMF; forestry by-products in OMF	Temperate agriculture; remote regions	SOC \uparrow up to ~ 25%; runoff \downarrow ; water retention \uparrow ; environmental pollution \downarrow ; production costs \downarrow via wood ash/bark/sawdust; biosolid/paper-mill composts improve soils	Clean-growth strategy; industry-university partnerships; grants	Field studies and programme reports	[42, 53, 90, 103, 108]
Brazil	Biochar-enriched OMF (coffee husk + acidulated apatite); compost variants	Field crops; PNRS-enabled plants	K leaching \downarrow 77%; GHG \downarrow 18%; maize yield \uparrow 30%; compost biomass \uparrow 26% with faster conversion; improved soil–water retention; mechanism: 200–400 m ² g ⁻¹ surface area + alkaline ash; LCA GHG \downarrow ~ 15% vs conventional	PNRS incentives; certified plants; technology transfer/training to African institutions	Field trials; LCA	[7, 26, 29, 30, 37, 64]
Argentina	Pelletised N- and P-enriched OMF; biochar-enriched blends	Mollisols; wheat and soy systems	Wheat yield \uparrow \approx 13% vs conventional; CEC \uparrow ~ 30%; SOC \uparrow 18%; microbial biomass \uparrow 22%; water retention \uparrow ; scaling needs regional biochar production, QA, training, demos; co-ops/PPPs as enablers	Cooperative and PPP models	Field trials; programme notes	[17, 38, 86]

Table 1 (continued)

Country/region	OMF type/formulation	Crop/system & context	Reported outcomes (Δ yield, Δ leaching/emissions, SOC, other)	Policy/enabler	Study design/duration	Citations
Kenya	Compost + modest mineral inputs; biochar-enriched packages	Smallholder maize; semi-arid resilience noted; humic Nitisols	Maize profitability/yield ↑ ~25%; N leaching ↓; dependence on synthetic N ↓; biochar packages: soil biodiversity ↑ ~50% and N leaching ↓ ~30%; P fractions improved; sorption ↓; seasonal N dynamics improved	Subsidies; training; microfinance; extension aligned with communal tenure and local norms	Field trials; socio-economic analyses	[23, 36, 68, 79]
Ethiopia	Community compost 4 t ha ⁻¹ + ½ mineral rate	Degraded SW highlands; maize	Yield ↑ ~40%; SOC ↑ ~27–30% (4 years); erosion ↓; water retention ↑; cooperative production lowered input costs; farmer-to-farmer exchange; microloans aid access; logistics/storage limit diffusion	Microloans; extension; community programmes; cooperatives	Multi-year field programmes	[13, 61, 68, 96, 111, 115]
Senegal	Compost-based OMF + full mineral; ridge cultivation	Basse-Casamance rice	Rice yield ↑ ~25%; Soil pH ↑ ~0.5	Cooperatives; local production	Split-plot field trials	[7]
Burkina Faso	Poultry-manure + urea OMF	Grain systems	Grain yield ↑; SOC ↑; microbial activity ↑; moisture retention ↑; costs ↓; scaling limited by credit/distribution; price instability discourages investment	Microfinance need; local production facilities; training	Field trials; programme notes	[23, 27, 68, 89]
Cameroon	Sludge- and organic-waste OMF; biochar-based OMF	Maize; regional farming systems	Soil fertility ↑; yields ↑; K leaching ↓ ~70% via sorption and aggregate stabilisation; water contamination risk ↓; scaling needs facilities and training	Local production facilities; farmer training	Field trials	[37, 74]
Madagascar	Biochar- and compost-enriched OMF	Upland rice; acidic soils; erratic rainfall	Soil pH stabilised; microbial activity ↑; yields maintained under stress; policy to promote sustainable fertiliser use; targeted training and local production facilities proposed; adoption limited by infrastructure/costs	PPP pathways; targeted training; local facilities	Field studies; programme notes	[5, 6, 16, 68, 83]
Southern Africa/ South Africa	Biofertilisers and OMF	Various; water spinach case; drought/erratic rainfall contexts	N fixation ↑; nutrient availability ↑; SOC ↑; N ₂ O ↓; <i>Pomoea aquatica</i> fresh weight ↑ 27.3%; soil-enzyme activity ↑; degraded-soil rehabilitation; water retention ↑; climate resilience ↑	Regional rehabilitation efforts in drought-prone systems	Field studies	[55, 84, 115]
India	Bioorganic fertilisers from industrial by-products (wet blue leather, potato peels)	Smallholder systems; community extension	Mean yield ↑ ~2.2%; growth and chlorophyll ↑ 15–25%; adoption > 30% in some regions; K-solubilising fungi/bacteria support nutrient supply; finance/infrastructure limit scale	Extension; community training; microcredit need	Field trials; adoption reports	[13, 49, 60, 68, 69]

Table 1 (continued)

Country/region	OMF type/formulation	Crop/system & context	Reported outcomes (Δ yield, Δ leaching/emissions, SOC, other)	Policy/enabler	Study design/duration	Citations
Sri Lanka	Nanofertilisers	Intensive rice	Rice yield \uparrow ~25%; N and P leaching \downarrow ~40%; broader uptake depends on production capacity and farmer training	Production-capacity expansion; farmer training	Field studies	[62] (Kotegoda et al. 2017)
China	Biochar-enriched OMF; nano-coated urea; biochar + high-Si coal ash	Rice; <i>pomoea aquatica</i> ; nutrient-recovery/precision policies	SOC \uparrow ; runoff \downarrow ; nitrogen-use efficiency \uparrow ; <i>pomoea aquatica</i> biomass \uparrow ~2.7%; K availability \uparrow ; sintering \downarrow with coal ash; policy support; training needs; costs/awareness constraints	Nutrient-recovery and precision policies; targeted subsidies/training recommended	Long-term and mechanistic studies	[12, 39, 55] (Kotegoda et al. 2017)
Indonesia	Microbial fertilisers (phosphate-/potassium-solubilising bacteria)	Reclaimed mining areas; residues near limestone mining sites used; maize and rice	Yield \uparrow ~18%; reliance on synthetic fertiliser \downarrow ; scale needs production capacity, training and market access; biotech access constraint	Production capacity; farmer training; market access; biotech access	Field trials	[37, 69]
Viet Nam	Diversified agroforestry systems (ICRAF guidance)	Mixed perennial-annual systems	Nutrient cycling \uparrow ; smallholder profitability \uparrow	ICRAF technical guidance; adoption support	Programme guidance; case evidence	[52]

Australasia, phosphate-solubilising bacteria (PSB) enhanced P availability without additional chemical inputs [62, 82].

Economic implications

Yield gains can translate into higher farm income (Table 2, 'Agronomic outcomes' and 'Economic effects'). Pelletised OMFs increased wheat yield and quality by $\approx 20\%$ compared with conventional fertiliser in a recent study [17]. In central Kenya, smallholder maize systems achieved roughly 25–40% higher yields when compost- or manure-based OMFs were supplemented with modest mineral nitrogen inputs [68]. In addition, on-farm trials indicate that integrating biochar into OMFs increased soil biodiversity by about 50% and reduced nitrogen leaching by $\sim 30\%$ in these systems, although high interest rates and poor logistics still limit scale-up [68, 79, 80].

Policy and institutional factors

Scalable uptake is supported by coherent policy and institutions (Table 2, 'Mechanism' and 'Intervention'; Table 3). The EU Nitrates Directive and related measures incentivise precision OMF use and reporting [104]. Brazil's National Solid Waste Policy (Lei 12.305/2010) channels resources into biochar-sewage-sludge recycling initiatives [15, 37]. In lower-income regions, micro-credit, cooperative finance and targeted subsidies remain important to overcome upfront costs [41, 68, 84].

Synergy and future directions

Bridging North–South disparities likely requires hybrid strategies that couple precision technologies with decentralised, low-cost organic recycling. Priority research needs include: (i) long-term OMF-microbiome interactions, (ii) affordable slow-release formulations for resource-constrained settings, and (iii) optimisation of biochar-PSB blends across agro-ecological zones. As indicated in Fig. 3, alignment of policy measures, infrastructure investment and cross-regional knowledge exchange may accelerate adoption while maximising agronomic and environmental benefits.

4.1.1 Europe: Policy-enabled adoption and outcomes

Adoption in Europe is supported by regulatory and infrastructure frameworks. The EU Nitrates Directive and Germany's Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) are associated with lower nitrate leaching and more efficient nutrient use [104, 114]. Biowaste recycling into OMFs and precision placement contribute to circular-economy goals [31, 104]. Work on landscape approaches and biodiversity co-benefits is emerging, alongside long-term, multi-site trials and studies with advanced formulations, including nano-enabled products [24, 62]. Regional practice includes the use of biowastes as OMF feedstocks in Poland and the United Kingdom [22]. Quantitative outcomes for Italy and the UK are summarised in the Results and Fig. 4; key barriers appear in Table 3 and policy levers in Table 4.

4.1.2 North America: Technological innovation and regulatory support

Adoption is bolstered by technology, incentives and regulation within circular-bioeconomy agendas [6]. Programmes in the United States and Canada promote collaboration across industry, academia and government [73]. Precision tools (e.g. GPS, sensors) have been reported to reduce wastage and improve efficiency [18, 108]. Research priorities include optimisation of pH, mineralogy and biological activity, and scaling of

Table 2 Field-verified performance of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMF): yield response and ecological co-benefits

Region	OMF formulation	Dominant crop(s)	Δ yield [%]	Study span*	Environmental & soil benefits†	Key insight	References
Brazil	K-enriched biochar OMF (coffee husk+acidulated apatite)	Maize	25–30	2 seasons	N ₂ O+CO ₂ -eq ↓ 18; K ⁺ leaching ↓ 77; soil-water retention ↑	High surface area and alkaline ash raise CEC and K ⁺ retention in sandy Oxisols	[37, 38]
United Kingdom	Sludge-based OMF	Wheat	~0 (maintained)	4 seasons	NO ₃ ⁻ leaching ↓ ~20; SOC ↑; GHG fluxes ↓; aggregate stability ↑	Mineral-equivalent yields with lower N losses	[31, 37]
Germany	Biochar/struvite/digestate OMF within precision systems	Wheat	15–20	Multi-year	N runoff ↓ 45; N ₂ O ↓ 7–10; K leaching ↓ ~70	Nutrient recovery plus site-specific placement reduces losses and raises yield	(Yan et al. 2023) [34, 37]
Italy	Phosphogypsum-enriched OMF (field crops)	Cereals/field crops	up to 25	Multi-site	Erosion ↓ ~15; soil pH ↑; P availability ↑	Ca ²⁺ /SO ₄ ²⁻ displace Al ³⁺ , improving P supply on acidic, erosion-prone soils	[4]
Italy	Humic-acid OMF (orchards)	Pomegranate	7–13	2 seasons	Trunk diameter ↑ +4.0 mm vs control (43.6 vs 39.6 mm; ≈10%); total phenolic content & antioxidant activity: no treatment effect; higher values in 2019 vs 2018 (year effect)	Veg-etative growth improved; quality metrics showed no treatment effect (year effect present)	[100]

Table 2 (continued)

Region	OMF formulation	Dominant crop(s)	Δ yield [%]	Study span*	Environmental & soil benefits†	Key insight	References
Senegal	Compost-based OMF (+ full mineral; ridge cultivation where noted)	Rice	~26	3 years	Soil pH ↑; soil biodiversity ↑ ~50 (incl. nematodes); salinity ↓ with ridging	Compost packages restore fertility and biota on acid-sulfate soils	[7, 23]
Ethiopia	Compost + mineral blend	Maize	~40	4 years	SOC ↑ ~27–30; erosion ↓; water retention ↑; GHG fluxes ↓ (dir.)	Ag-gregate formation and protection of nascent humics underpin SOC gains	[61, 96, 115]
Kenya	Compost + mineral blend; biochar-enriched packages	Maize	~25	4 seasons	N leaching ↓ ~30; soil biodiversity ↑ ~50; input cost ↓	Package management under extension improves NUE and resilience in rain-fed systems	[68]
Canada	Compost-mineral OMF	Mixed temperate crops	nd	Multi-site	SOC ↑ up to ~25; runoff ↓; soil structure/ water retention ↑	Compost integration elevates SOC and hydrological function in temperate systems	[53]

Table 2 (continued)

Region	OMF formulation	Dominant crop(s)	Δ yield [%]	Study span*	Environmental & soil benefits†	Key insight	References
United States	OMF within precision placement/irrigation; enhanced-efficiency N	Maize/row and high-value crops	~ 10	Multi-year	Reduced N and P leaching under zone-specific variable-rate irrigation; improved nutrient-use efficiency; benefit size depends on soil and management; equipment costs constrain small farms	GPS-guided timing and dose improve NUE and curb gaseous losses	[1, 34, 105, 108]
China	Bio-OMF (water spinach)	<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i>	~ 27 (biomass)	Multi-season	Soil properties improved; nutrient status \uparrow	Bio-OMF raises biomass in leafy vegetables	[55]
Denmark	Compost + mineral (7.5 t ha ⁻¹ compost example)	Cereals	dir. \uparrow	Field seasons	Plant height \uparrow ; crown diameter \uparrow ; grain yield \uparrow	Compost addition supports growth and yield in regional trials	[88]
Morocco	Semi-liquid OMF (olive-mill wastewater)	Maize	nd	1 season	Polyphenol load \downarrow ; microbial respiration \uparrow	Waste-derived nutrients recycled on clay soils with detox benefit	[14]
Argentina	Pelletised N/P-enriched OMF; biochar-enriched variants	Wheat; soy systems	\approx 13 (wheat)	Field trials	CEC \uparrow ~ 30; SOC \uparrow 18; microbial biomass \uparrow 22; water retention \uparrow	Slow-release matrices sustain N; added P stimulates rooting	[17, 86]
Cameroon	Sludge/organic-waste OMF; biochar-based OMF	Maize	dir. \uparrow	Field trials	K leaching \downarrow ~ 70; water-contamination risk \downarrow	Sorption and aggregate stabilisation reduce K losses	[74]

Table 2 (continued)

Region	OMF formulation	Dominant crop(s)	Δ yield [%]	Study span*	Environmental & soil benefits†	Key insight	References
Burkina Faso	Poultry-manure + urea OMF	Grain crops	dir. \uparrow	Field trials	SOC \uparrow ; microbial activity \uparrow ; moisture retention \uparrow	Locally sourced inputs lower cost and improve soil function	[27, 89]
Madagascar	Biochar/compost-enriched OMF	Upland rice	maintained	Field seasons	Soil pH stabilised; microbial activity \uparrow	Blends maintain yields under erratic rainfall on acidic soils	[83]

*season = one crop cycle

†Direction of change shown where only direction is reported; nd, no quantitative yield change reported in the source; NUE, nitrogen-use efficiency; SOC, soil organic carbon; GHG, greenhouse-gas emissions

residue-based OMF production systems [46]. Table 3 summarises operational barriers and tested responses; Table 4 lists enabling instruments.

4.1.3 Asia: Localised solutions and scaling challenges

Progress has been reported in the use of industrial by-products and bio-organic mineral fertilisers in India, China and Indonesia [49, 55, 60, 69]. Infrastructure and market access remain major constraints, similar to parts of sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America [60, 73]. Immediate food-security pressures can favour mineral inputs, yet policy development, infrastructure investment and targeted R&D offer opportunities to tailor OMF formulations to local soils and climates [84]. Table 3 summarises barriers and tested responses; policy levers are listed in Table 4.

4.1.4 Africa and the wider Global South: constraints and scaling pathways

Locally adapted OMF systems address soil degradation and resource constraints, yet adoption in parts of sub-Saharan Africa remains below 20%. Recurrent barriers include limited formal credit (\approx 12% of Kenyan smallholders), expertise gaps, unreliable supply chains and weak transport infrastructure that raises delivered costs; decentralised composting capacity often falls short of demand. Scalable responses include biowaste-valorisation hubs and pairing composting facilities with microloans, which in Ethiopia delivered higher yields and improved soil health. Efficient N and P management remains central in arid WANA contexts; transfer of microbial solutions from Asia (K- and P-solubilising bacteria) is promising. Ecological responses reported for Madagascar include increases in omnivorous nematodes under bio-OMFs. Policy support for waste-to-fertiliser conversion is identified as a lever in several African settings. Regional barriers and field-tested interventions are synthesised in Table 3; policy levers appear in Table 4; the adoption framework is shown in Figs. 6, 7 [7, 13, 14, 61, 68, 69, 73, 83, 84, 87, 111].

Table 3 Comprehensive barrier-intervention and regional evidence map for organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs)

Region/country	Representative OMF/technology	Barrier (category)	Mechanism/context	Intervention	Agronomic outcomes	Environment-tal & LCA outcomes	Economic effects	Risks & controls	Evidence (citations)
Germany/EU	Biowaste-to-OMF pellets; precision placement	Regulatory—harmonised compliance/reporting tools	Strong regulatory drivers; nitrate leaching curtailed; implementation benefits from shared templates	Share reporting tools across states	Not reported	Reduced nitrate losses in regulated systems	Not reported	Not reported	[104]
United Kingdom	Sludge OMF with GPS placement	Technological—access to precision tools	Affordability/access limits for small farms	Low-cost GPS kits; operator training	Yields ≈ mineral NPK; evidence of lower N run-off (~20%); potential cost savings where mitigation costs fall	Not reported	Input savings at field scale	Not reported	[31]
United Kingdom	Sludge-derived OMF (cereals)	Infrastructure/Logistics—sludge → OMF chain maturity	Mature chain enables consistent supply and field use	Replicate sludge-OMF plants; strengthen logistics	Yields comparable with mineral NPK	N run-off ↓ ~20% vs mineral fertiliser	Savings where mitigation costs fall with lower run-off	QA/QC for bio-solids-derived products	[31]
Poland	Sludge-ash OMF (P source)	Standards/Quality—QC and compliance	NPK comparable with mineral; metals below EU limits	Standardised QA/QC; certification	Plant-available P ≈ superphosphate	LCA: lower GHG vs producing equivalent mineral NPK	Break-even aided by gate-fee revenue at central plants	Metals control via testing and standards	[50]
Italy	Phosphogypsum-enriched OMF with organic matrix	Technological—pelletising/coating capacity	Performance depends on access to coating/pelletising	Invest in pelletising; validate controlled-release coatings	Yield ↑ ~25%; soil pH ↑ ~0.4; erosion ↓ ~15%	Replacement of mined phosphate where PG is recycled	Cost reduction where subsidies or existing lines operate	Product safety via standards and process control	[4, 63]
Morocco	Semi-liquid OMF from olive-mill waste + rock phosphate	Technological—pilot capacity and know-how	Fermentation/nutrient-recovery steps need pilot infrastructure	Regional pilot plants; technology transfer	Not reported	Phenols ↓ ~92%; plant-available P ↑ ~35%	Local value added	Process control limits phenolics	[14]

Table 3 (continued)

Region/country	Representative OMF/technology	Barrier (category)	Mechanism/context	Intervention	Agronomic outcomes	Environmental & LCA outcomes	Economic effects	Risks & controls	Evidence (citations)
Ethiopia	Hydrothermal-carbonised (HTC) ag-waste OMF (maize)	Technological—local reactors and R&D capacity	Diffusion depends on local manufacture/maintenance	Fund regional R&D; technician training	Yield ↑ ~ 40%; input cost ↓ ~ 25%	Not reported	Lower unit cost at pilot scale	Maintenance/training reduce downtime	[61]
Senegal	Compost-mineral blend (acid-sulfate soils, rice)	Knowledge/Extension—site-specific blending	Effective use requires locally attuned guidance	Farmer-led training; advisory materials	Rice yield ↑ ~ 25%; soil pH ↑ ~ 0.5	Not reported	Not reported	Misapplication risk mitigated by training	[7]
Burkina Faso	Poultry manure + urea (upland rice)	Knowledge/Extension—combined organic-mineral use	Dosage/timing knowledge conditions performance	Integrate combined-input guidance in extension	Grain yield ↑ ~ 30%; weed pressure ↓	Not reported	Not reported	Misapplication risk mitigated by guidance	[89]
Brazil	PNRS-enabled compost/biochar hubs	Standards/Quality—formal OMF standards	Supply chains formed; scaling needs clear standards	National OMF standard; labelling	Not reported	Not reported	~BRL 100 m public/private investment	Standards cut transaction costs	[15, 42, 110]
Brazil	K-enriched sludge-biochar granules (slow-release K)	Technological—process and safety management	Slow-release K reduces leaching; handling needs SOPs	Dust-risk controls; sealed silos; earthing	Maintained yields in relevant systems	Slower K release; curtailed K leaching vs MOP	Local value capture via pilot production	SOPs mitigate dust risk	[37]
Kenya	Compost+ mineral packages (smallholder systems)	Financial—limited access to credit	~ 12% of smallholders have formal loans; affordability constrains uptake	Microfinance; co-op credit; targeted vouchers	Yield benefits reported in case studies	Not reported	Improved input purchase capacity	Financial literacy supports repayment	[68]
Sub-Saharan Africa	OMF supply and distribution	Infrastructure/Logistics—roads and transport	~ 34% of rural roads are all-weather; transport mark-ups + 30–50%	Decentralised plants near feedstocks; feeder-road upgrades	Not reported	Not reported	Lower distribution cost with shorter hauls	Not reported	[7, 110]
Global South	Weak extension services	Knowledge/Extension—service capacity gaps	Limited reach slows correct timing/dosing	Strengthen public extension; peer field schools; mobile apps	Better practice in trials/programmes	Reduced losses where advice followed	Not reported	Not reported	[61, 84]

Table 3 (continued)

Region/country	Representative OMF/technology	Barrier (category)	Mechanism/context	Intervention	Agronomic outcomes	Environmental & LCA outcomes	Economic effects	Risks & controls	Evidence (citations)
Global South	Limited farmer education	Knowledge/Extension—awareness and safety	Low awareness of benefits and safe handling	Workshops; radio campaigns; peer mentoring	Not reported	Mis-application reduced with training	Not reported	Safety guidance lowers risk	[13, 84]
Global South	Land tenure security	Regulatory—insecure land tenure	Uncertain rights discourage long-term investment	Accelerated land registration; legal support	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported	Legal clarity supports multi-year management	[5, 13]
Global South	Market access and price realisation	Infrastructure/Logistics—restricted market access	Fragmented markets depress farm-gate prices and reinvestment	Marketing cooperatives; streamlined regional trade policy	Not reported	Not reported	Improved reinvestment capacity	Collective bargaining improves terms	[73, 110]
Cross-regional	Sludge-to-OMF; PG-based OMF; compost/biochar OMF	Regulatory & quality standard gaps	Inconsistent rules/labels slow approvals and trust	National OMF standards; ISO-aligned QA/QC; clear labelling	Not reported	Metals/contaminant control; lower losses with slow-release	Lower transaction costs with clear specs	Standards/certification build buyer confidence	[50, 98]

Table 4 Policy levers enabling OMF adoption

Lever	Purpose	Operational channel	Evidence (citation)
Subsidies for OMF products and blending (SUB)	Reduce capex/opex and end-user price	Targeted product/plant subsidies; cost-share for blending lines	Phosphogypsum-OMF programme; product price approximately 20% lower [63], precision support linked with ~ 15–20% higher crop yields and about 15% lower nitrogen leaching in field trials [17, 31]
Tax credits & fiscal rebates (TAX)	Improve project economics for plants and upgrades	Corporate tax credits; VAT rebates for waste-to-OMF conversion	PNRS-aligned fiscal measures for sludge/biowaste valorisation [15], plant-level upgrades documented in sludge-to-fertiliser deployments [50]
Low-interest credit & guarantees (LOAN)	Ease liquidity constraints for farmers/SMEs	Seasonal loans; guarantee funds; co-op microfinance; input vouchers	Microloans raised maize profit margin by 28% [68]; co-op/credit access noted as enabler of adoption [13, 27, 61]
National OMF quality standards & labelling (STD)	Assure performance/safety; lower transaction costs	National standard aligned with ISO; certification; clear labels	Compliance with limits and labelling supports market entry [50, 98]; procurement efficiency and trust gains reported for certified products [42]
Reporting & monitoring under nutrient directives (REG)	Align nutrient use with environmental limits; enable benchmarking	Compliance templates; audits under N-directives/water rules	EU Nitrates frameworks tied to lower N losses in field programmes [104]; verified runoff ↓ ~ 20% in UK sludge-OMF trials [31]
Waste policy & feedstock access (EPR/PNRS)	Secure organic residues for OMF inputs	PNRS-style recovery targets; municipal routing of biowaste	National waste policy enabled certified plants and steady feedstocks [15], circular-economy sourcing described for OMF chains [37]
Decentralised processing near feedstocks (DECENT)	Cut logistics cost; stabilise local supply	Regional compost/biochar/OMF hubs; municipal concessions	30 kt yr ⁻¹ sludge converted to marketable OMF with metals < EU limits [50]; rice yield ↑ 25% after hub deployment [7]; disposal fees ↓ 35% at olive-waste bioreactors [14]
Biogas-digestate linkage (EEG/DIG)	Ensure steady digestate for OMF blending	EEG incentives; co-digestion plants integrated with OMF lines	a network of biowaste digestion and co-digestion plants supplies digestate for OMF blending within precision-farming systems [91, 114]
Public extension & farmer training (EXT)	Improve timing/dose/handling; raise adoption capability	Field schools; radio/mobile advisories; peer networks; MRV-light	Yield ↑ 40% and input cost ↓ 25% with app-supported compost/biochar guidance [61]; on-farm schools improved practice and outcomes [68]; community training documented [7, 84, 89]
Access to precision placement services (PREC)	Increase nutrient-use efficiency and yields	Cost-share GPS/variable-rate kits; operator training	N losses ↓ ~ 15% and yields ↑ ~ 10% in precision programmes [8], adoption supported via US CSP/EQIP [28], verified field performance in UK trials [31]
Feeder-road & logistics upgrades (LOG)	Reduce delivered cost; avoid stock-outs	Rural road upgrades; fertiliser corridors; storage nodes	Transport and corridor planning cited as prerequisites for stable input supply and lower delivered prices [110]
Market integration & co-operative marketing (MKT)	Improve price realisation; enable reinvestment	Support co-ops; streamline regional trade procedures	Co-operative models and regional trade facilitation linked with higher uptake and better margins [73, 110]
Land-tenure formalisation (TENURE)	Enable long-term soil-health investment	Land registration; para-legal support; tenure documentation	Tenure security associated with investment in soil improvements and input adoption [5, 13]
Pilot funding & technology transfer (TT/R&D)	De-risk innovation; adapt designs to context	Innovation grants; pilot plants; public-private consortia; open protocols	Pilot lines for K-enriched sludge-biochar [37]; technology pilots and bioreactors funded with measured cost/impact benefits [14]; harmonised protocols reduce duplication [41]
Environmental market instruments (CARB/NUT)	Monetise climate and water benefits	Mobile MRV carbon pilots; nutrient-trading for P hotspots	MRV cost < USD 1 t ⁻¹ CO ₂ e [44]; nutrient-trading frameworks and watershed pilots reported [41, 115]

Fig. 3 Regional adoption of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs) versus policy/subsidy support. Adoption index: 1 = low, 2 = medium, 3 = high (years as reported, 2010–2024). Data sources: Europe [22, 104], North America [6, 108], Asia [55, 60, 69], Africa [7, 13, 68], South America [37, 38, 78], Australia & New Zealand [62, 93, 112]

Fig. 4 Comparative economic and yield effects of organo-mineral fertiliser (OMF) adoption in selected field studies. Yellow bars show reported cost savings (% change vs mineral-fertiliser control; study definition of costs), orange bars show yield increase (% vs control). Countries and crops are indicated on the x-axis; labels display central estimates from each source. Inputs and calculation notes are provided in Supplementary Tables S3-S4. Data sources: Deeks et al. [31], Fachini et al. [37], Mucheru-Muna et al. [68], Badiane et al. [7], Mamuye et al. [61]

4.1.5 South America: Sustainable agriculture and biochar innovations

The region emphasises soil health, yields and bio-based products (e.g., sugarcane bio-ethanol) within circular-economy frameworks [10, 37]. Policies and infrastructure vary across countries [37]. Recovered agro-industrial by-products are used to improve nutrient efficiency and waste valorisation. Barriers and enabling measures are summarised in Tables 3 and 4.

4.1.6 *Australia and New Zealand: Microbial interventions and nutrient efficiency*

Phosphate-solubilising bacteria (PSB), including *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas*, increase P availability in low-P soils and can produce plant growth-promoting and antifungal compounds [82, 93, 112]. Evidence from New Zealand links PSB diversity with soil P status under P deficiency [62]. Integrating microbial inputs with compost- or biochar-based organo-mineral fertilisers can enhance nutrient recycling and system resilience, consistent with circular economy objectives. Adoption benefits from targeted collaboration, region-specific formulation and farmer training. Operational constraints and field-tested responses are summarised in Table 3; policy levers are listed in Table 4.

4.2 **Global adoption of OMFs: policy, infrastructure, and market growth**

This section reviews global adoption of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs) across market growth, regional strategies, technological pathways and policy interventions. Projections for 2024 value the OMF market at about USD 2.1 billion in Europe, USD 1.3 billion in Asia–Pacific and USD 0.8 billion in Africa. FAO scenarios indicate that Asia–Pacific and sub-Saharan Africa could absorb roughly 80% of the net increase in fertiliser demand to 2022, while another outlook attributes a comparable share to Asia and Latin America, exposing capacity gaps in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa [41]. Global food demand is expected to grow by about 60% by 2050. Industry responses are region-specific: BASF SE develops high-efficiency products for mature markets and cost-effective lines for emerging ones, Dow couples precision nutrient management with nanotechnology-enhanced fertilisers for high-value crops in Europe and intensive systems in Asia; Evonik Industries AG offers biodegradable coatings that control nutrient release in water-limited regions [9, 106].

4.2.1 *Market structure and pricing*

Economy lines for emerging markets range from USD 200–350 t⁻¹, targeting affordability while meeting core agronomic needs. Transport costs linked to infrastructure quality can add up to 20% [108]. Higher upfront costs may be offset by reduced mineral-fertiliser use, improved soil fertility and lower compliance costs. In the United Kingdom, sludge-derived OMFs maintained crop yields while reducing nitrogen runoff by approximately 20% in field trials [31]. Figure 5 shows projected global market expansion from 2021 to 2029, from about USD 650 million to over USD 900 million, corresponding to a 5.8% CAGR [28].

4.2.2 *Technology cases and agronomic performance*

In China, nanohydroxyapatite-enriched OMFs improved phosphorus availability and crop yields while reducing nutrient runoff. Precision nutrient management in Germany minimised leaching and raised resource efficiency [34, 114]. Italy reports phosphogypsum-enriched OMFs that neutralise soil acidity and raise yields by about 25% within subsidy-backed deployment [4]. In Ethiopia, combining compost with mineral fertilisers raised maize yields by roughly 40% compared with conventional mineral fertilisation. Figure 4 collates these yield and cost effects across countries [7, 31, 37, 61, 68].

Fig. 5 Projected global OMF market value, 2021–2029 (million USD). Line reproduces the published series; CAGR \approx 5.8% as reported by the source. Assumptions and currency adjustments are detailed in Supplementary Table S3. Data source: Data Bridge Market Research [28]

4.2.3 Bio-based industries and process innovation

Bio-based industries anchor OMF supply in both regions, with differing approaches. High-income settings convert biowaste into high-efficiency fertilisers that cut environmental impacts and production costs under circular-economy objectives [63]. In Poland, hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC) of biowaste on silty loam increased nutrient-use efficiency by about 30% and improved N and P availability. Reported production costs fell by approximately 25%, expanding farmer access [22]. Case studies indicate HTC-based fertilisers lifting maize yields by 28% and wheat yields by 22%. In Ethiopia, integrating HTC with locally available residues reduced fertiliser costs by about 20% [22, 61]. Compost-biochar packages lowered fertiliser costs by about 35% versus synthetic alternatives, raised maize yield efficiency by around 40%, ameliorated acidity, enhanced water retention and stimulated microbial activity important for nutrient cycling [61, 115]. In Kenya, compost-based OMFs increased vegetable yields by 28%, while interest rates and logistics still limit scale [68].

4.2.4 Finance, standards and collaboration

Scaling requires technology transfer adapted to local conditions and targeted finance for R&D. Germany's EEG and Brazil's National Solid Waste Policy (PNRS) illustrate complementary levers. The PNRS statute (Brasil MMA 2010) earmarks BRL 100 million for regional composting hubs and sets phased recycling targets, which secure OMF feedstock supply [37]. Clear national OMF standards and ISO-aligned QA/QC reduce transaction costs and support buyer confidence, as detailed in Table 3. Limited access to centralised processing plants sustains the role of decentralised, community-driven methods in low-resource settings, although scale and consistency remain constrained. Impact-monitoring systems are needed to track socio-economic and environmental

outcomes. EU-Africa R&D initiatives back the transfer of advanced options such as bio-char-enhanced fertilisers to diverse agro-ecologies. Comparative analysis across cases indicates that large-scale adoption rests on combining high-efficiency technologies from the Global North with cost-effective, resource-based packages from the Global South.

4.3 Overcoming barriers and scaling OMF adoption: strategies and future directions

The successful adoption of OMFs varies significantly across regions due to differences in technological capacity, financial accessibility, and socio-economic structures. While the Global North benefits from advanced recycling technologies, precision agriculture, and robust policy frameworks, the Global South faces challenges related to underdeveloped infrastructure, limited financial resources, and uncertain land tenure. Addressing these disparities requires a combination of localised solutions, financial interventions, and knowledge-sharing mechanisms that facilitate the adaptation of Northern innovations to Southern contexts while leveraging the South's expertise in community-driven nutrient recycling.

4.3.1 Technological, financial, and socioeconomic barriers

The following summaries group adoption determinants under technology, finance and socioeconomic conditions and link each point to the evidence cited below.

4.3.1.1 Technological barriers The Global South faces limited access to advanced nutrient recycling technologies, such as struvite recovery systems, which are widely used in the Global North for phosphorus recycling (Yan et al. 2023). For instance, Uganda's underdeveloped OMF processing capacity constrains nutrient recovery and agricultural productivity [13, 68]. In contrast, Germany's bio-waste recycling systems and precision agriculture tools enable efficient nutrient application and environmental sustainability [34]. Even in developed regions, some farmers remain hesitant to switch from synthetic fertilisers, fearing temporary yield reductions during the initial transition period [61].

4.3.1.2 Financial barriers Restricted financial access is a critical barrier, with only 12% of Kenyan smallholder farmers having access to formal credit, limiting their ability to invest in improved fertilisers [68]. High interest rates further discourage borrowing, making OMF adoption financially unfeasible for many farmers. Conversely, Brazil's microloan initiatives demonstrate how tailored financial mechanisms can empower smallholders, reduce financial risks, and enhance productivity [37]. Subsidized credit schemes, modeled on Italy's OMF incentive programs, could accelerate local adoption and foster economic viability [4].

4.3.1.3 Socioeconomic barriers Factors such as insecure land tenure, weak market infrastructure, and inadequate farmer training hinder widespread OMF adoption in the Global South. For example, Ethiopian farmers hesitate to invest in soil restoration due to uncertain land ownership [13]. Community-driven composting programs have successfully improved maize yields, offering cost-effective and scalable alternatives [61]. In Malawi, poorly developed market networks and lack of agricultural training prevent farmers from accessing OMFs, highlighting the need for improved extension services and educational initiatives [97]. Kenya's pelletized bio-waste fertilisers, tailored for local soil

conditions, have improved crop yields and helped restore degraded land, contributing to local food security [68, 86].

4.3.1.4 Educational initiatives Extension programmes and farmer training are essential to overcoming scepticism and ensuring long-term adoption of organo-mineral fertilisers. Regional workshops, field demonstrations, and online training modules led by governments, universities, and fertiliser companies facilitate standardized knowledge dissemination. Tailored curricula adapted to local contexts enhance awareness and build confidence in OMF efficacy.

4.3.1.5 Summary of key barriers

- Technological: Limited access to advanced recycling systems [e.g., struvite recovery in sub-Saharan Africa; (Yan et al. 2023)].
- Financial: Restricted credit access (e.g., Kenya: only 12% of smallholders have access to formal credit [68]) and high interest rates.
- Socioeconomic: Poor market infrastructure and insecure land tenure (e.g., Ethiopia [13]).

Adapting Northern technological innovations to local contexts while leveraging the South's expertise in nutrient recycling can enhance adoption. Concise national programme notes and adoption constraints are summarised in Table S5 (Supplementary).

4.3.2 Regional differences between the Global North and South

The adoption of OMFs differs between the Global North and the Global South, influenced by technological capacity, policy frameworks, resource availability and environmental conditions. Key drivers and constraints are summarised in Table 3.

4.3.2.1 Global North High-income regions benefit from advanced infrastructure and regulatory support, such as the EU Circular Economy Package and Germany's Renewable Energy Sources Act [6]. Precision agriculture tools and nanofertilisers optimize nutrient use, reducing runoff while maintaining high yields [98]. Yield improvements from biochar-enriched OMFs have been documented in Germany and Italy.

4.3.2.2 Global South Lower-income regions struggle with inadequate infrastructure, limited technology access, and financial constraints. Frequent droughts and nutrient-poor soils further complicate OMF adoption. Decentralized and community-driven solutions, such as biochar and compost-based fertilisers, have been instrumental in addressing soil degradation and improving productivity [68, 88].

Key differences:

- Policy and Infrastructure: Strong regulatory support in the North enables large-scale OMF production, while the South lacks cohesive policies or financial incentives.
- Technology: Biowaste recycling and precision agriculture are well-established in the North, while the South relies on decentralized, community-led initiatives [37].
- Financial Resources: The North has access to subsidies and credit, while the South faces credit scarcity and financial risks [68].

Investments in decentralized biowaste recycling, region-specific training programs, and accessible financing mechanisms can reduce adoption disparities. Collaborative frameworks integrating Northern technological advancements with Southern localised knowledge facilitate adoption and support sustainable agricultural development globally.

4.3.3 Localised solutions and literature insights on OMF adoption

Localised solutions that blend traditional practices with OMF technologies provide practical alternatives for regions facing infrastructure and financial constraints.

- Senegal's compost-based projects have successfully improved rice yields, demonstrating the effectiveness of region-specific soil amendments.
- Biochar initiatives in Ethiopia enhance soil structure and nutrient retention.
- Kenya's microfinance-supported community initiatives achieved notable yield improvements [68].
- Brazil's biochar techniques, adapted for African agricultural systems, highlight the importance of technology transfer [37].

Efforts to recycle agricultural residues into OMFs align with circular economy principles. For example:

- Phosphogypsum-enriched compost enhances nutrient retention and soil structure [4].
- Microbial interventions during composting optimize pollutant removal, producing semi-liquid OMFs for nutrient-deficient soils [14].

Cross-regional knowledge-sharing expands the impact of these localised initiatives. Decentralized production facilities, using locally available materials, lower costs and logistical barriers [50].

Training programs led by governments, academic institutions, and fertiliser companies should standardize knowledge dissemination through:

1. Workshops
2. Online training modules
3. Field demonstrations

Such initiatives are expected to raise OMF adoption rates and help ensure that solutions are tailored to specific agro-ecological conditions.

4.3.4 Global collaboration and knowledge exchange

Global collaborations, including the EU's Horizon 2020 program and FAO initiatives, have played a key role in advancing OMF adoption. Efforts focus on technology transfer, capacity building, and public-private partnerships, integrating advanced technologies with localised solutions to tackle region-specific agricultural challenges. The programs facilitate technology transfer, as seen in biochar-enriched OMF trials in African soils, which improved maize yields by 26% and mitigated environmental degradation [34]. FAO-led cross-regional initiatives provided training in OMF application, and follow-up monitoring in participating programmes reported higher rates of correct application among trainees, supporting the value of sustained extension [41, 43, 109].

Adopting technologies like struvite recovery from wastewater sludge in Germany has demonstrated cost-effective phosphate recycling methods, with potential for replication in the Global South. Targeted funding to establish decentralized micro-infrastructure for sludge processing, supported by low-interest credit schemes similar to Italy's subsidy models, can facilitate this transition (Yan et al. 2023) [4].

Effective knowledge exchange relies on adaptable technology and adequate financial backing. Biochar-enriched OMFs deliver marked gains in nutrient retention and soil fertility, yet high upfront costs limit access in many regions. Expanding microloan schemes and providing low-interest financing, as demonstrated in Brazil, enabled smallholders to raise maize yields by 25% while reducing environmental degradation [61].

In Ethiopia, government-supported training programs for community-led composting increased maize yields by 40% over 4 years and enhanced soil organic carbon by 27%, demonstrating the importance of integrated technical and financial support [61].

Strengthening global collaboration involves harmonizing policies across regions to minimize regulatory barriers and establish standardized OMF quality certifications. Investments in research and development for scalable technologies, including semi-liquid OMFs enriched with microbial formulations designed for resource-limited settings, are fundamental to advancing adoption [14]. Expanding agricultural extension services ensures farmers acquire the necessary skills to effectively implement OMF technologies, enhancing both adoption rates and long-term sustainability. Investments in decentralized production facilities and knowledge-sharing platforms can help ensure innovations address specific agro-ecological needs, fostering resilience and sustainability in marginalized areas.

Figure 6 shows the critical factors influencing OMF adoption globally, comparing advanced technology adoption in the Global North with localised, cost-effective solutions in the Global South. The diagram illustrates the interplay of policy, financial mechanisms, and infrastructure in shaping implementation strategies across diverse agricultural systems.

4.3.5 Scaling OMF adoption through waste-to-value innovations

Scaling the adoption of OMFs globally necessitates the integration of waste-to-value innovations with targeted policy support, decentralized infrastructure, and capacity-building initiatives. Waste-to-value technologies, including struvite recovery, biochar production, and anaerobic digestion, are key to advancing the circular economy (Yan et al. 2023) [37]. For instance, Morocco's decentralized processing hubs transform wastewater sludge into semi-liquid OMFs, significantly reducing logistical costs and improving rural accessibility [14]. Expanding such technologies globally requires targeted infrastructure investments and operator training to ensure scalability and sustainable impact.

Key waste-to-value technologies

1. Struvite recovery

- Application: Effective in regions with wastewater and phosphate-rich industrial by-products.
- Scalability: Requires low-cost, decentralized micro-infrastructure for sludge processing, paired with training programs for operators.

Fig. 6 Key policy, economic and technological factors shaping adoption of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs) across regions. Mind-map contrasting Global North and Global South; branches list adoption factors, challenges, strategies/policies, outcomes and future research

- Example: Germany's struvite recovery reduced phosphate waste by 30% while producing high-value fertilisers (Yan et al. 2023).

2. Biochar production

- Application: Suitable for semi-arid regions with abundant biomass residues.
- Scalability: Small-scale pyrolysis units offer low-cost solutions, reducing dependence on centralized facilities.
- Example: Brazil's biochar-enriched OMFs increased crop yields by 25% and improved water retention in tropical soils [37].

3. Anaerobic Digestion

- Application: Ideal for converting animal slurry and organic municipal waste into biogas and nutrient-rich digestate.
- Scalability: Co-located digesters near livestock farms or urban centers optimize logistics.
- Example: Cyprus transformed pig slurry into biogas, improving maize yields by 15% and extending nutrient release by 30 days (Yan et al. 2023).

4.3.5.1 Decentralized processing and local adaptation Decentralized biowaste processing facilities lower logistics costs and improve access to OMFs in rural areas. In Morocco, wastewater sludge processing into semi-liquid OMFs enhanced maize yields while addressing waste management inefficiencies [14]. Supporting such initiatives requires well-structured operator training modules. Workshops that integrate hands-on experience with digital resources ensure consistent product quality and effective technology deployment, particularly in low-resource settings.

4.3.5.2 Policy and financial incentives Government subsidies and tax credits help reduce production costs and encourage adoption. In Italy, field trials with phosphogypsum-enriched OMFs improved soil health and increased crop yields by about 25% [4], suggesting that financial incentives could help scale up such waste-to-value fertiliser technologies. Similarly, Brazil's National Solid Waste Policy (PNRS, Brasil, 2010) mobilized tannery waste into biochar production, improving nutrient management while reducing environmental risks [37, 64].

4.3.5.3 International collaboration and knowledge exchange Cross-regional partnerships enable the transfer of waste-to-value technologies to regions facing similar challenges. Brazil's Embrapa projects successfully adapted biochar techniques for African soils, addressing nutrient deficiencies and improving soil structure [37]. Such collaborations exemplify the potential of joint innovation in creating scalable, context-specific solutions.

4.3.5.4 Environmental and economic incentives Carbon-credit and nutrient-trading schemes link waste-to-value practices with financial returns, adding an economic dimension to sustainable land management [44, 115]. Their performance is highly context dependent. Smallholder projects depend on low-cost monitoring, reporting and verification; a Kenyan pilot reported transaction expenses above USD 12 t⁻¹ CO₂e, which erased profits [115]. FAO trials in Kenya calculated initial MRV costs of more than USD 8 ha⁻¹ unless farmers operate through aggregator cooperatives [40]. Nutrient-trading markets also require baseline discharge permits and transparent enforcement, capacities now present in only three African countries. The Chesapeake Bay pilot needed 5 years of regulatory alignment and stakeholder commitment before the first trades occurred [44]. A phased roll-out that starts with donor-funded demonstrations, combines extension services with digital MRV and builds institutional capacity can reduce early-stage risks before national scaling.

The recommendations outlined in Table 4 underline the importance of policy frameworks, financial mechanisms, and international cooperation for advancing OMF adoption. Financial incentives, including subsidies and microcredit systems, address cost barriers that hinder adoption among smallholder farmers. Decentralized infrastructure (local biowaste processing hubs) reduces logistical constraints and enhances fertiliser availability in underserved regions. The following subsections consolidate agronomic mechanisms with on-farm applications, ensuring that each recommendation speaks directly to production realities (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Conceptual framework of drivers of OMF adoption in the Global North versus Global South. Colours denote domains: environmental (green), economic (blue) and policy (orange); arrows indicate within-region pathways and cross-regional linkages, with icons marking typical examples

4.3.6 Practical implications for agriculture, policy, and innovation systems

This section integrates key findings and outlines strategies to advance the global adoption of OMFs through targeted approaches in agriculture, policy, and technological innovation.

Governments play a critical role in fostering OMF adoption. Germany's Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG) provides incentives for biowaste recycling, linking environmental objectives to increased agricultural productivity [114]. Italy's subsidies for phosphogypsum-enriched fertilisers have reduced costs and increased crop yields by 25% [4]. In the Global South, addressing financial constraints through expanded microloan programs and low-interest credit can significantly boost adoption, as seen in Kenya, where only 12% of smallholders access formal credit [68]. Standardized certifications and traceability in the Global North build trust in OMF products, facilitating market growth and international trade compliance [98].

Technological advancements tailored to specific contexts effectively address agricultural challenges. In nutrient-depleted and semi-arid regions, biochar improves water retention and cation exchange capacity, while compost enhances soil organic matter, boosting fertility and resilience [14, 61]. Decentralized biowaste processing units and small-scale anaerobic digesters provide cost-effective alternatives for regions with limited infrastructure [68].

Infrastructure development remains central to scaling adoption. Establishing decentralized biowaste processing facilities minimizes logistical expenses and improves fertiliser availability in remote agricultural areas [50]. Enhanced rural transportation networks, as seen in Uganda, address inefficiencies that otherwise impede broader adoption of OMFs [7].

Access to finance remains a key challenge. Brazil's microfinance initiatives show how subsidized loans enable smallholders to adopt biochar-enriched OMFs, increasing yields by 25% and reducing financial risks [37]. Partnerships between governments, financial institutions, and NGOs can replicate these successes globally.

Collaboration among governments, research institutions, and private sector actors drives innovation. Poland's hydrothermal carbonization technology, which improved nutrient efficiency by 30% and reduced costs by 25%, demonstrates the value of targeted R&D investments [22]. Cross-regional knowledge exchange, exemplified by Brazil's Embrapa initiatives, has adapted biochar technologies for African contexts, enhancing soil health and food security [37].

OMF adoption has been associated with improved food-security metrics and lower greenhouse-gas emissions in the contexts studied [8, 14]. A phased approach, near-term subsidies and microloans, medium-term collaboration and long-term research, is proposed to support sustainable agricultural transformation.

4.3.7 Future research priorities and directions

Future research on OMFs should focus on long-term scientific and socio-economic impacts, particularly in the Global South, where environmental and structural constraints hinder adoption. Multi-year studies on nutrient cycling, soil microbiomes, and carbon sequestration can provide a clearer assessment of OMFs' role in mitigating climate change and improving soil health [112]. The prevalence of short-term trials in the literature has left critical gaps in understanding long-term ecological and economic outcomes, especially in sub-Saharan Africa [14].

Decentralized, low-cost facilities can enhance phosphogypsum utilization, reduce logistical challenges, and improve waste management efficiency [50, 63]. Assessing the cost-effectiveness of these systems for smallholder farmers and exploring their integration into existing agricultural frameworks will provide actionable insights for sustainable scaling.

Socio-economic dimensions of OMF adoption require further examination. The impact of OMFs on income stability, food security, and resilience to market volatility or climatic shocks should be explored [14]. Access to credit, markets, and infrastructure is necessary for scaling adoption. Studies should evaluate how OMFs can reduce reliance on imported fertilisers and stabilize smallholder economies, particularly during periods of price instability [5].

Digital technologies, including remote sensing, IoT systems, and machine learning, hold transformative potential for optimizing OMF application. Precision nutrient delivery tailored to field conditions reduces waste and improves efficiency [68]. Integration into smallholder systems, depends on affordability and user-friendly designs. Research should prioritize adapting these technologies to local needs and developing training programs that facilitate widespread adoption and usability.

Policy-driven incentives like carbon credits, nutrient trading, and payments for ecosystem services (PES) represent promising pathways for supporting sustainable OMF adoption. Linking OMF use to carbon offset markets can provide additional income streams for farmers while promoting climate mitigation [44, 115]. PES initiatives should be studied for their potential to enhance biodiversity and soil health while delivering direct financial benefits to participants.

Research must integrate practical field applications to achieve real-world impact. Farmer-centered approaches that incorporate participatory research help tailor solutions to local needs. Innovations in microbiology that enhance microbial diversity for nutrient release should be combined with socio-economic analyses to improve adoption

rates and outcomes. Aligning these strategies can position OMFs as a key component of sustainable agriculture, potentially addressing regional challenges and contributing to global food security objectives.

Table 5 organises research priorities into six themes that link mechanistic questions with implementable outputs. The themes cover soil-microbiome interactions under OMF regimes; release kinetics and carrier chemistry, including nano-additives; carbon stabilisation in biochar-OMF blends; product safety and contaminant fate; residue-driven, decentralised production with circular metrics; and digital MRV-light with evaluation of policy instruments. Each theme specifies target deliverables aligned with field use, including biomarker and sampling protocols, diffusion-sorption datasets by soil

Table 5 Priority research themes to advance organo-mineral fertiliser (OMF) innovation and adoption

Research priority	Key knowledge gap	Target deliverable	Anticipated agronomic & environmental benefit	References
Soil microbiome dynamics and nutrient cycling	Seasonal interaction of OMFs with phosphate-solubilising and N-fixing consortia in degraded or semi-arid soils; how microbial guilds respond to composite inputs	Field-calibrated formulation rules aligned with dominant functional guilds; standard sampling/biomarker protocol (enzyme panels, qPCR/metabarcoding) across crop stages	Faster P and N turnover, higher SOC, more stable yields under stress; better nutrient-use efficiency in smallholder systems	[13, 68, 84, 112]
Release kinetics and carrier chemistry (incl. nano-additives)	How biochar/apatite/nano carriers govern NPK release and sorption across pH-texture contrasts; translation from columns to field	Open diffusion-sorption parameters and validated datasets across major soil classes; guidance for carrier selection and rate setting; field protocols for leaching plots	Fewer applications, lower leaching and volatilisation, reduced labour and input cost; rate/timing optimisation in coarse and fine soils	[38, 67, 74, 92, 105]
Carbon stabilisation via biochar-OMF blends	Mechanisms securing long-term C in micro- and macro-aggregates under OMF regimes; link between biochar properties and aggregate hierarchy	Quantified C-persistence indices tied to biochar traits; aggregate fractionation + MIR/ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ tracing workflow for field trials	Durable SOC gains, higher CEC, improved structure and resilience to drought	[56, 96, 103]
Product safety and contaminant fate	Thresholds and behaviour of metals and organics in sewage- and tannery-based OMFs; simple, rapid QA at plant gate	Harmonised quality standard and pass/fail limits; rapid diagnostics (field kits + lab confirmation) and batch-release checklist	Safe nutrient recycling, higher buyer confidence, clearer market access	[50, 57, 98]
Residue-driven, decentralised production with circular metrics	Matching local residues (olive-mill effluent, sludge, compost) to simple reactor designs; siting/logistics and LCA at village-hub scale	Design blueprints for hub-scale plants, feedstock-to-product mapping, and OMF-specific LCA templates; TEA assumptions made explicit	Lower haulage cost, higher local value capture, evidence-based investment and siting; waste risk reduction	[6, 7, 14, 50, 94, 106, 117]
Digital MRV-light and policy-instrument effectiveness	Suitability of low-cost sensors/apps for smallholders; measurable impacts of credits/trading/extension on adoption and emissions	Open-source advisory with simple indicators and MRV-light workflow; quasi-experimental evaluations of carbon credits and nutrient trading; reporting templates	Optimised rates and timing, reduced runoff and N_2O , equitable uptake; robust evidence to tune subsidies/loans/standards	[44, 68, 88, 98, 108, 115]

SOC—soil organic carbon; CEC—cation-exchange capacity; LCA—life-cycle assessment; TEA—techno-economic analysis; MRV—measurement, reporting and verification

class, aggregate-based carbon-persistence indices, harmonised QA/QC with rapid diagnostics, hub-scale LCA/TEA templates, and open-source advisory workflows.

Table 6 collates evidence on OMF performance across regions, structured by adoption context, life-cycle results, risk profile, economic effects, and climate contributions. Reported field outcomes include lower nitrate leaching with maintained yields in the UK and Germany, improved farm margins with compost-plus-mineral packages in Kenya, higher yields with HTC-based blends in Ethiopia, slower K release with reduced leaching in Brazil, and reduced CH₄ in flooded rice in Morocco [14, 31, 37, 61, 68, 104]. Soil-carbon gains are reported where OMF use is sustained [68, 115]. Contaminant and handling risks are managed through standards, QA/QC, and operating procedures, including metal limits for PG- and sludge-based products and safety measures for bio-char storage and transfer [37, 50, 57, 63, 98]. Policy and market instruments that organise feedstocks and de-risk investment are documented in the case studies [4, 42].

Economic evaluations demonstrate OMFs' dual role in enhancing productivity while maintaining cost efficiency. In high-income regions, precision formulation technologies improve nutrient optimization, whereas in resource-limited areas, localised production models ensure affordability and accessibility. Empirical data indicate that decentralized biowaste processing facilities reduce logistical costs and enhance farmer adoption rates [14, 50]. Climate contributions position OMFs within global sustainability strategies. Their role in circular economy practices decreases reliance on synthetic fertilisers, mitigates emissions, and supports climate-adaptive agricultural models [44, 115]. Nutrient recycling mechanisms further minimize environmental degradation associated with nitrogen and phosphorus overuse, aligning with global regulatory directives [68]. A structured synthesis of these dimensions establishes an evidence-based foundation for policymakers, researchers, and industry leaders to refine OMF implementation strategies. Empirical insights guide the development of region-specific policies, targeted research agendas, and financial models that maximize OMF adoption while ensuring long-term sustainability and resilience in agricultural systems.

4.3.8 Limitations of the study

This study has limitations related to data availability, regional variability, and the generalizability of findings. Evidence on OMF adoption is affected by inconsistent reporting in resource-limited settings and by reliance on secondary sources that may omit emerging practices. Many studies are short-term, which constrains inference on long-term sustainability. Given heterogeneity in designs, outcomes and reporting, pooled estimates were not calculated; results are presented as ranges or medians, and uncertainty reported in the source articles (e.g., confidence intervals, standard errors) is retained where available. For example, Sub-Saharan Africa lacks systematic agricultural reporting systems, producing fragmented or outdated datasets that can bias assessments of OMF impacts [99]. Future studies should prioritize comprehensive primary data collection through randomized, multi-season field trials in under-researched regions.

The variability in soil characteristics, climates, and cropping systems limits the broad applicability of OMF research findings. Granular, sub-regional analyses and comparative studies across diverse agroecological and socio-economic contexts are crucial for developing tailored strategies. For instance, nutrient-depleted soils and erratic rainfall patterns in Sub-Saharan Africa necessitate region-specific approaches to OMF application,

Table 6 Regional insights, life-cycle results, risks, economic effects, and climate contributions of organo-mineral fertilisers (OMFs)

Section	Region/context	Evidence-based insight (quantitative where reported)	Implication	Citations
Regional disparities in adoption	Germany (Global North)	Biowaste plants pelletising sewage sludge into OMFs were associated with $\approx 15 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ lower nitrate leaching (cereal systems)	Regulatory backing and processing capacity coincide with reduced N losses	[104]
	United Kingdom (wheat)	Sludge-derived OMFs maintained grain yields \approx mineral NPK and reduced N runoff $\approx 20\%$; additional trials report N_2O $\downarrow 15\%$ and NO_3^- leaching $\downarrow 15\%$ vs urea/mineral baselines	Field performance comparable to mineral fertiliser with lower losses	[31]
	Kenya (smallholders)	Compost + mineral strategy raised maize profit margins by 28%	Blended OMF approaches can improve farm economics	[68]
	Ethiopia (maize)	Hydrothermal-carbon (HTC) bio-OMF increased grain yield by 40% and reduced input costs by 25%	Local HTC hubs can enhance returns and affordability	[61]
	Burkina Faso (upland rice)	Poultry-manure OMF increased grain weight by 30%; weed pressure \downarrow	Low-cost organo-mineral blends deliver gains in resource-limited settings	[89]
	China (vegetable, water spinach)	Rice-straw biochar + NPK boosted biomass by 18% and soil microbial biomass C by 22%	Biochar-enriched OMFs support crop growth and microbial functioning	[55]
	India (tomato)	Leather-waste NPK pellets improved biomass and enabled chromium recycling (waste-to-value)	By-product streams can supply nutrients while closing material loops	[60]
	Poland (Eastern Europe)	Sludge-ash OMF supplied plant-available P \approx superphosphate; Cd and Pb below EU limits	Recovered-P OMFs can substitute mineral P within safety thresholds	[50]
Life-cycle assessment (LCA)	Production (Poland)	Converting sewage sludge to OMF emitted fewer GHG than producing equivalent mineral NPK (process-level LCA)	Waste-to-OMF pathways can lower cradle emissions	[50]
	Production (PG processing, Russia)	Processing phosphogypsum into OMF reduced landfill disposal and displaced mined phosphate	PG-to-OMF improves waste management and resource substitution	[63]
	Field application (Brazil)	K-enriched sludge-biochar granules released K more slowly and curtailed K leaching vs MOP (slow-release behaviour)	Slow-release OMFs mitigate nutrient losses	[37]
	End of use (Kenya; maize systems)	Repeated compost-OMF applications increased SOC by $\approx 30\%$ over several seasons	Soil-carbon accrual accompanies sustained OMF use	[68]
Risk profile	PG-based pellets	Cd concentrations below EU thresholds reported	Compliance achievable with PG-derived OMFs under QA/QC	[63]
	Sludge-derived pellets (Poland)	Products complied with Zn limits	Metals manageable under standard quality control	[50]
	Pilot production (Brazil)	Dust-explosion precautions required for biochar handling (sealed silos, earthing straps)	SOPs reduce process-safety risk in biochar operations	[37]
	Olive-mill-waste OMF (Morocco)	Fermentation lowered phenolics (-92%) and raised plant-available P ($+35\%$); mitigated microbial inhibition	Pre-treatment improves product safety and efficacy	[14]

Table 6 (continued)

Section	Region/context	Evidence-based insight (quantitative where reported)	Implication	Citations
Economic effects	Farmer practice (Kenya)	Participatory training reduced N over-application incidents	Extension improves nutrient stewardship and reduces losses	[68]
	Centralised facility (Poland)	Gate-fee revenue helped a sludge-pellet plant reach breakeven within a few years	Tipping-fee models support financial viability	[50]
	Decentralised hubs (Ethiopia)	HTC hubs produced bio-OMF at lower unit cost than urea-based fertilisers (with yield ↑ 40%)	Local manufacture reduces delivered cost and supports scaling	[61]
Climate contributions	Smallholders (Kenya)	Compost + mineral packages reduced fertiliser expenditure and increased maize income	Blended strategies improve net returns	[68]
	Policy context (Brazil)	National Solid Waste Policy stimulated municipal composting and created rural employment opportunities	Policy support catalyses supply chains and jobs	[42]
	UK field trials	Sludge-derived OMFs lowered direct N ₂ O vs ammonium nitrate; other trials show N ₂ O ↓ 15% and NO ₃ ⁻ ↓ 15% relative to mineral baselines	Potential GHG mitigation at field scale alongside leaching control	[31]
	Morocco (flooded rice)	Olive-waste OMF reduced CH ₄ emissions	Processed-waste OMFs can curb methane in paddy systems	[14]
	Ethiopia (Nitisols)	Biochar-enriched OMF enhanced soil-carbon sequestration	SOC gains contribute to mitigation and resilience	[115]
	Resource substitution	Recycling phosphogypsum into OMF displaces mined rock phosphate (upstream footprint reduction)	Material substitution lowers embodied impacts	[4, 63]
	Global outlook	Scenario work indicates that wider OMF adoption could reduce agricultural GHGs and support multiple SDGs (context-dependent)	System-level gains depend on context and scale	[41, 44]

as demonstrated by studies emphasizing the unique requirements of these soils [59, 75]. By contrast, temperate regions with established infrastructure and precision agriculture systems offer different contexts for OMF integration.

Key aspects, including cumulative effects on soil microbial diversity, carbon sequestration, and nutrient cycling over multiple growing seasons, remain underexplored. Short-term trials often show immediate yield improvements, yet comprehensive studies are needed to assess OMFs' capacity to restore degraded soils and sustain productivity over decades [37, 54]. Evaluating their impact on soil health parameters, such as microbial diversity and phosphate solubilization, can provide insights into their role in sustainable nutrient management under climatic stressors.

Socio-economic barriers, such as limited credit access and logistical challenges, alongside insufficiently explored policy frameworks, hinder OMF adoption in resource-constrained regions. Future studies should prioritize evaluating scalable financial mechanisms, like microfinance programs, and the adaptation of subsidies and regulatory incentives to diverse socio-economic contexts. Although credit access and infrastructure deficits are acknowledged as significant constraints, quantitative analyses of their extent remain scarce. Research should evaluate scalable microfinance models, such as those highlighted by Bouhia et al. [14], to facilitate smallholder farmers' access to OMFs. Decentralized production systems utilizing local biowaste, as proposed by Kominko et al. [50], require further assessment to determine their economic viability and potential

to improve rural livelihoods. Analyzing these dynamics will yield practical strategies for developing scalable, inclusive OMF adoption programs tailored to diverse agricultural contexts.

The policy landscape influencing OMF adoption is underexplored. While subsidies and regulatory incentives have been shown to accelerate adoption in developed regions, their adaptation to resource-constrained contexts remains unclear. Future studies should examine how policy instruments (carbon credits and nutrient trading schemes) can be effectively implemented. Future research requires a multi-disciplinary approach integrating agronomic, ecological, and socio-economic analyses. Long-term, regionally tailored field trials combined with advanced data analytics could yield more reliable results and support evidence-based decision-making.

5 Implications and priorities

Evidence across regions links organo-mineral fertilisers with higher nutrient-use efficiency, yield gains and lower emissions, with effect sizes dependent on crop, soil and formulation. Adoption remains uneven; trajectories are shaped by technological capacity, infrastructure, finance and local socio-economic context. Precision tools and recycling programmes have supported uptake in high-income settings, while decentralised production and community initiatives are pivotal where supply chains are thin. Access improves with targeted finance, streamlined regulation, product standards and sustained extension.

In high-income regions, precision agriculture and recycling programmes have supported uptake; in lower-income settings, underfunded community initiatives highlight the need for coordinated efforts. Expanding financial support, enabling decentralised production and strengthening rural infrastructure can improve access for smallholders and broaden use. Supportive policy frameworks and capacity-building are decisive: financial incentives (e.g., subsidies, tax relief), streamlined regulations and farmer training facilitate equitable implementation. Investments in biowaste-processing capacity and transport infrastructure reinforce supply chains. National experiences in Germany and Brazil illustrate that policy support coupled with strong extension can increase uptake and help translate agronomic potential into realised benefits.

The global potential of OMFs relates to multiple sustainability objectives. Work summarised here reports that OMFs help maintain soil fertility, support diverse microbiomes and reinforce nutrient cycling [5, 44]. Biochar-enriched formulations can stimulate phosphate-solubilising bacteria and N-fixing microorganisms, improving nutrient availability and supporting longer-term soil-organic-carbon gains [54, 56, 62]. In degraded, semi-arid soils, OMF application has been linked to lower nutrient leaching, reduced greenhouse-gas emissions and less erosion [53, 115]. Field trials with phosphogypsum-based OMFs in North Africa reported reduced runoff and appreciable yield gains under challenging conditions [4, 7].

Actionable priorities emerging from the literature include:

- Scalable and cost-effective production models: Region-specific production that valorises agricultural residues and industrial by-products such as olive-mill effluent and poultry manure offers cost-effective OMF pathways [14, 25]. Decentralised facilities can shorten supply chains and lower operating costs, widening access in

resource-limited areas [73]. Integrating local feedstocks embeds manufacture in circular-economy loops and helps keep products affordable [106].

- Food security and smallholder livelihoods: Field trials in several African settings report crop-productivity gains with OMF packages under specified rates and blends; where profitability was measured, net returns for smallholders increased [7, 61, 68, 89]. Effects depend on formulation, soil and management. Many farmers lack affordable finance; targeted credit, stronger co-operatives and well-designed subsidies can improve access.
- Advancing precision-agriculture technologies: Digital tools coupling IoT sensors, remote sensing and machine-learning have been reported to reduce nutrient losses by roughly 20–30% in temperate prototypes, suggesting transferability as affordability improves [78, 102, 108]. Modular, open-source approaches can spread investment and foster local service ecosystems.
- Policy mechanisms for climate mitigation: Carbon credits, nutrient trading and payments for ecosystem services can accelerate adoption while contributing to mitigation targets [40, 98]. Incentives that valorise phosphogypsum in arid agriculture were associated with ~15% lower fertiliser costs and ~20% higher yields in pilots [4, 66]. Alignment with local resource streams and monitoring capacity increases credibility and uptake.
- Interdisciplinary research and collaboration: Progress depends on programmes that connect soil science with socio-economics and governance [10, 73]. Participatory trials have lifted adoption where farmers co-adapt formulations and application methods [44, 61, 108]. Credible climate-finance instruments require budgets for monitoring, reporting and verification, regulatory oversight and farmer-centred extension [40].

Future research directions include:

- i. long-term studies of OMF effects on microbial diversity, SOC stabilisation and nutrient-cycling efficiency in degraded and nutrient-poor regions;
- ii. evaluation of decentralised, low-cost production hubs using local residues and industrial by-products, with attention to cost-effectiveness and scalability;
- iii. socio-economic analyses of credit, co-operative models and subsidies that reduce financial barriers, and of OMF contributions to income stability and food security;
- iv. development of affordable precision-agriculture toolkits tailored to low-infrastructure contexts (remote sensing, IoT, machine learning); and
- v. policy design for carbon credits, nutrient trading and PES, together with harmonised quality standards and certification to strengthen market trust and trade.

Bridging the gap between advanced technologies prevalent in the Global North and resource-efficient innovations needed in the Global South will require coordinated efforts across research, policy and finance. Continued innovation, removal of adoption barriers and equitable access to OMFs is critical for scaling sustainable fertilisation and can thereby contribute to improved food security while reducing environmental pressures.

Abbreviations

OMFs	Organo-mineral fertilisers
SOC	Soil organic carbon

GHG	Greenhouse gas
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
EEG	Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (Renewable Energy Sources Act, Germany)
IoT	Internet of Things
PNRS	National Solid Waste Policy (Brazil)
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
PSB	Phosphate-solubilising bacteria
NPK	Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium (fertiliser components)

Supplementary Information

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Supplementary Material 1.

Author contributions

K.C. conceptualized the study, designed the methodology, and supervised the research. K.C. conducted the literature review, analyzed the data, and wrote the main manuscript text. K.C. prepared all figures and tables. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable. This study is a review article and does not involve human participants or animals.

Consent for publication

Not applicable. This study does not include data from individual persons.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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